

Extraction of Gallium(III) and its Separation from Indium(III) and Thallium(III)

G. N. MULIK, S. R. KUCHEKAR and M. B. CHAVAN*

Analytical Laboratory, Department of Chemistry,
Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

Manuscript received 15 November 1985, revised 25 August 1986,
accepted 13 November 1986

THE solvent extraction separation of gallium(III) from aqueous chloride media with high molecular weight amines has been reported¹⁻⁷. Trioctylamine⁸, trilaurylamine⁹, Amberlite LA-2¹⁰ are also used for extraction separation of gallium(III) from different aqueous media. The present work describes the use of *N*-*n*-octylaniline as an extractant for gallium(III) from hydrochloric acid media. The proposed method is simple, rapid and selective and can be used for the separation of gallium(III) from indium(III) and thallium(III).

Experimental

Gallium(III), indium(III) and thallium(III) solutions were prepared and standardised as described earlier¹¹⁻¹³. *N*-*n*-Octylaniline was prepared by the method of Gardlund¹⁴; a 3% (v/v) solutions were prepared using benzene as diluent.

General procedure: To an aliquot of solution containing upto 2.14 mg of gallium, sufficient hydrochloric acid and water were added to have 6.0–10.0 *M* acid concentration in a volume of 20 ml. Gallium(III) was extracted by shaking for 1 min with a 3% solution of *N*-*n*-octylaniline in benzene (10 ml). The benzene layer separated and gallium was stripped off from the organic phase by shaking for 1 min with water (2×20 ml). The combined washings were treated with a measured excess of 0.001–0.01 *M* EDTA in a conical flask at pH 2.5±0.5 adjusted by adding dilute ammonia solution and back-titrated with 0.001–0.01 *M* thorium nitrate using 0.1% xylenol orange (7 drops) as an indicator.

Results and Discussion

Gallium(III) was extracted from 1.0–10.0 *M* hydrochloric acid with 1–3% (v/v) *N*-*n*-octylaniline in benzene. It was observed that 3% reagent in benzene extracts gallium quantitatively from 6.0–10.0 *M* hydrochloric acid with 1 min shaking. Of the various solvents used as diluents under the optimal conditions of extraction benzene, xylene and IBMK gave 100.00% extraction while the extraction of gallium was 98.00, 92.30 and 74.34% for toluene, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform, respectively. Benzene was selected as the diluent as it gave clear phase separation.

Nature of extracted species: The plots of log *D* vs log *C* (*N*-*n*-octylaniline concentration) for 3 and 4 *M* hydrochloric acid medium gave slopes 1.2 and 1.16, respectively, indicating the formation of $[\text{RR}'\text{NH}_2^+\text{GaCl}_4^-]$ species. The tetrahedral GaCl_4^- ion is already known in aqueous solution^{15, 16}.

Effect of diverse ion: Tolerance limits for different ions were set at the amount required to cause an error of less than 2%. For the extraction of 1.07 mg gallium, 10 mg of each of Be^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and Sr^{2+} ; 6 mg of each of Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Se^{2+} , W^{6+} , Ge^{4+} and UO_2^{2+} ; 5 mg of each of In^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , As^{3+} , Mo^{6+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Th^{4+} and VO^{2+} ; 4 mg of Au^{3+} ; 1 mg of each of Rh^{3+} , Pt^{4+} , Os^{8+} were tolerated. Common anions, such as (100 mg each) fluoride, phosphate, sulphate, nitrate, tartarate, ascorbate, citrate malonate, thiosulphate, acetate, oxalate, thiourea and thiocyanate; and 30 mg of EDTA, had no interference. Interference due to Al^{3+} could be masked with citric acid. Interference due to Fe^{2+} and Cr^{6+} could be eliminated by their reduction with sodium thiosulphate.

Extraction scheme for the separation of Ga^{3+} , In^{3+} and Tl^{3+} : A solution containing Ga^{3+} , In^{3+} and Tl^{3+} was placed in a separating funnel and sufficient hydrochloric acid was added to make its concentration 0.7 *M* in the final volume of 15 ml. Thallium(III) was first extracted from aqueous solution by shaking for 1 min with a 3% *N*-*n*-octylaniline in benzene (10 ml). Under these conditions, gallium and indium remain in the aqueous phase. Thallium from the organic phase was stripped with 0.2 *M* acetate acetic acid buffer solution (2×45 ml) and determined complexometrically¹³. Sufficient concentrated hydrochloric acid was added to make the aqueous phase 6 *M* acidic and then gallium(III) was extracted and determined by the procedure already described. Indium(III) in the aqueous phase was determined complexometrically¹³. Binary and ternary mixtures of gallium (0.53–1.07 mg), indium (1.02–5.70 mg) and thallium (1.02–2.04 mg) of various compositions were prepared. Triplicate analysis of these mixtures shows that the average recovery of indium is 99.73±0.27% and that of gallium and thallium 99.99±0.01%.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the U. G. C., New Delhi, for providing a fellowship to one of the authors (S. R. K.).

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* Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad 431 04.

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Extraction of Palladium(II) with the Liquid Cation-exchanger Versatic 10

JYOTIRMOY MAJUMDER and UDAY SANKAR RAY*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235

Manuscript received 18 October 1985, revised 14 March 1986,
accepted 13 November 1986

SOLUTIONS of versatic acids in organic solvents behave as liquid cation-exchangers, the exchange properties of which are similar to those of organic ion-exchange resins. They have been used in our laboratory for the extraction of di-, tri-, and tetra-valent metals^{1,2}. However, no systematic attempt has yet been made to study the extraction behaviour of palladium(II) with versatic acids³. In this communication a rapid method for the extraction of milligram amounts of palladium(II) with the liquid cation-exchanger, Versatic 10 in benzene has been proposed.

Experimental

Elico LI-10 pH meter was used for pH measurement.

Versatic 10, a mixture of C₁₀ isomeric tertiary monocarboxylic acids, had the concentration and the purity of 5.2 M and 99%, respectively⁴. It was standardised by the usual acid-alkalimetric titration. Solutions of Versatic 10 were prepared in benzene. Versatic 911, a mixture of saturated tertiary C₉, C₁₀ and C₁₁ monocarboxylic acids⁴, and SRS 100 (equiv. wt. 260–290), a high molecular weight synthetic carboxylic acid, supplied by Shell Chemical, were used without further purification. Palladium(II) solution (4.8 mg ml⁻¹) was

prepared by digesting PdCl₂ (Ranbaxy) (0.85 g) with 2 N HCl (20 ml) and then diluted to 100 ml. The solution was standardised by the complexometric titration with EDTA (disodium salt) by a back-titration procedure with standard 0.01 M Th(NO₃)₄ using xylenol orange indicator⁵.

Extraction procedure: The aqueous phase contained 4.8 mg of palladium(II) in 0.1 M sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of pH 6. pH was further adjusted when required by dilute sodium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made up to 20 ml bringing the ultimate concentration of palladium in the aqueous phase to 2.4 × 10⁻³ M. The solution was equilibrated with 0.834 M Versatic 10 in benzene (1 : 6, 10 ml) for 10 min by manual shaking. Settling time was 10 min. The organic phase was stripped with concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 ml) for 1 h by a mechanical shaker. After equilibration, the phases were settled (5 min) and the aqueous phase was separated. The amount of palladium was estimated from the acid extract complexometrically.

Results and Discussion

The extraction of palladium(II) with Versatic 10 was performed at various pH at constant acetate (0.1 M) and extractant concentrations. Extraction of palladium increases with increased pH and becomes quantitative at pH 5.75. The distribution ratio (*D*) and the percentage of extraction of palladium(II) at different pH are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION OF Pd^{II} AS A FUNCTION OF pH

pH	Versatic 10—Benzene (1 : 6)		Versatic 10—n-Hexane (1 : 6)	
	Extraction of Pd ^{II} %	Distribution ratio (<i>D_{Pd}</i>)	Extraction of Pd ^{II} %	Distribution ratio (<i>D_{Pd}</i>)
3.5	2.4	0.05	0.5	0.01
4.0	2.8	0.05	35.7	1.1
4.5	42.8	1.5	57.6	2.7
4.75	48.1	1.8	75.2	6.2
5.0	61.9	3.2	86.7	13.0
5.25	76.2	6.4	95.2	39.6
5.5	97.6	81.3	97.8	88.9
5.75	99.6	498	97.8	88.9

The effect of extractant on extraction was studied by varying the concentration of Versatic 10 from 0.026 to 0.834 M. A plot of log *D* vs log [Versatic 10] gives a straight line of slope 0.9. Shibata and Nishimura⁶ showed that Versatic 10 in organic diluent exists as a dimer (R₂H₂). The extraction mechanism of palladium(II) can therefore be proposed as

Among the diluents tested with Versatic quantitative extraction was achieved only in case of benzene